

Towards a sustainable workplace: a life cycle perspective on EV-charging-integrated HVAC systems

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A life cycle assessment was conducted for promoting sustainable workplace.
- Sensitivity analysis identified key parameters affecting HVAC and EV charging.
- Solar-driven energy systems reduce climate change impact by 87.28%.
- User behaviour on HVAC and charging strongly shapes workplace energy impacts.

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ABSTRACT

Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems contribute substantially to energy consumption and carbon emissions in the building sector. This study evaluates the environmental impacts of solar-powered HVAC systems in the workplace in a city in Portugal (Sines) using a comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA), compared to systems powered by national grid electricity. The LCA is performed using the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method with a cradle-to-grave system boundary. Electric vehicle chargers are included to temporarily store excess electricity generated from a solar photovoltaic system. Results from the LCA indicate that the manufacturing and operation phases of the product system powered by grid electricity contribute significantly to most of the environmental impacts, while switching to a solar-powered system could reduce the climate change impact by 87.28%. The sensitivity analysis demonstrates that heating and cooling set point temperatures of HVAC systems critically affect the environmental burdens arising from the product system. Substituting reclaimed refrigerants for newly produced refrigerants can reduce global warming potential by 5.8% during the manufacturing phase of HVAC systems. Enhancing HVAC energy efficiency and adapting heating and cooling operation are essential for reducing GHG emissions. Furthermore, the scope of the study is expanded by evaluating the environmental impacts of workplace HVAC systems in three more different European cities, i.e., Paris, London, and Oslo, representing warm and cold climate zones. Future increases in renewable electricity capacity lead to reduced environmental impacts but increase mineral and metal resource use. A broader consideration of environmental impacts through LCA offers insights into the future development and application of sustainable energy systems.

1. Introduction

Building sectors accounted for 30% of the world's final energy demand and 37% of global CO₂ emissions due to energy consumption in buildings operation and material production [1]. Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems are the primary contributor, accounting for approximately 38% of buildings' energy use [2]. The floor area in building sectors is expected to increase by 75% between 2020

and 2050, along with a growing number of HVAC systems [3]. To align with the European Union's Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, which mandates highly energy-efficient and zero-emission buildings by 2050 [4], decarbonising HVAC systems is crucial for mitigating CO₂ emissions from buildings and achieving this goal. Meanwhile, electrification is widely accepted as a primary approach for the decarbonisation of buildings [5]. The HVAC systems in residential and commercial buildings have increasingly shifted towards electric solutions, e.g., vapor-compression systems for cooling [6], and mechanical systems for

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Nomenclatures		Abbreviations	
A_{PV}	Area of the solar PV panels, m^2	AC	Air conditioner
BC_{EV}	Battery capacity of electric vehicle, kWh	CFCs	Chlorofluorocarbons
$CF_{i,k}$	Characterisation factors of the k^{th} substance in the i^{th} impact category	COP	Coefficient of performance
Eff_{charging}	Charging efficiency, %	EER	Energy efficiency ratio
Eff_{PV}	Module efficiency, %	EV	Electric vehicle
f_{charging}	Charging frequency of one electric vehicle in one year, n times	GHG	Greenhouse gases
Irr	Solar irradiance, W/m^2	GWP	Global warming potential
M_k	Mass of the k^{th} substance consumed or emitted	GWP 100	Global warming potential over a 100-year horizon
n_{EV}	Number of electric vehicles	HCFCs	Hydrochlorofluorocarbons
P_{HVAC}	Capacity of HVAC systems, kW	HFCs	Hydrofluorocarbons
P_{PV}	Power output of PV plant, kW	HVAC	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning
s_i	Impact scores of the i^{th} impact category	IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
$t_{\text{operation}}$	Operational time, hour	LCA	Life cycle assessment
$W_{\text{elec.charging}}$	Electricity charged to electric vehicle, kWh	LCI	Life cycle inventory analysis
$W_{\text{elec.cooling}}$	Electricity consumption for delivering cooling, kWh	LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
$W_{\text{elec.grid}}$	Electricity output from grid to chargers, kWh	PV	Photovoltaic
$W_{\text{elec.heating}}$	Electricity consumption for delivering heating, kWh	SOC	State of charge
		VOC	Volatile organic compounds
		VRV	Variable refrigerant volume

ventilation to supply fresh air from the exterior [7]. In addition to space heating which is predominantly provided by fossil-fuel driven furnaces and boilers, commercially available electrified heating options include electric heaters and heat pumps [8]. Unlike electric heaters, which directly convert electricity into thermal energy, heat pumps utilise external low-temperature heat sources and raise them to a higher temperature by consuming work [9]. The electricity demand of these systems raises concerns regarding the primary energy sources used for electricity production, particularly when they are derived from fossil fuels. Therefore, promoting carbon-free or renewable energy sources for electricity generation is essential to support electrification as an effective tool for achieving zero-emission HVAC systems [2].

Numerous innovations have facilitated the development of both grid-connected and stand-alone renewable energy-powered HVAC systems [10]. A solar integrated power, cooling and heating system, which fully utilises solar irradiation to meet both electrical and thermal energy demands, offers a promising solution to the energy crisis [11]. Rooftop photovoltaic (PV) systems have been successfully integrated with heat pumps to supply domestic heating and cooling [12]. Solar PV systems can also be installed at building sites to support ground source heat pumps [13], air conditioning [14], ventilation air preheating [15], and more. Hucklebrink et al. [16] proposed guidelines for decarbonising the residential heating sector, demonstrating that a combination of solar PV, heat pumps, and hydrogen technologies offers a more cost-effective alternative to building refurbishment. To balance the energy supply and demand profiles of solar PV electricity and energy end users, energy storage solutions are commonly employed. These include batteries and thermal energy storage, which can enhance grid stability and maximise the self-consumption rate of solar PV electricity [17]. Solar electricity can be stored directly in electrical storage devices, such as electric vehicles (EVs) batteries, which enables EVs to act as short-term energy storage system. This synergy between EV batteries and PV provides additional flexibility and further stabilises the daily energy supply from solar generation [18].

Recent works on solar-assisted EV charging have primarily focused on the protocols to control the grid connection, charging standards, and smart charging strategies [19]. The strategies are mainly used to adjust tariff rates in real time to shift charging between peak and off-peak hours, thereby improving cost effectiveness and energy efficiency. A feasibility analysis of solar energy for residential area with EV charging

was conducted by integrating economic and electrical parameters to overcome the peak load challenges [20]. In office buildings, EV charging and HVAC operation typically coincide during working hours, leading to overlapping peak electricity demand that may align with peak solar PV generation. Utilising on-site solar energy sources can smooth up the electricity demand peak and reduce reliance on the external power grid. Therefore, integrating solar energy with HVAC systems and EV charging can decarbonise workplace energy supply, provide cost-effective storage options, and increase the overall electrical storage capacity [21]. Dynamic simulation tools have been developed to model such integrated systems, including solar-assisted heat pumps and EV charging stations, to meet combined heating, cooling, and electrical energy demands [22]. Furthermore, the co-adoption of HVAC systems, EV charging, and renewable energy technologies has been investigated under social and behavioural factors, such as risk tolerance, pro-environmental behaviour, and energy knowledge [23]. These studies have largely focused on integrating different climate solutions, aiming to achieve CO₂ emissions reductions during the operation phase, by assessing energy performance, identifying key drivers, and optimising system design. However, the production, deployment, and end-of-life stages of the components in these integrated systems still require substantial non-renewable energy and material resources, resulting in environmental impacts that extend beyond climate change alone [24].

Beyond the operation phase, the integrated HVAC systems pose several environmental concerns, one of which arises from the production and disposal of refrigerants [25]. Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) have been widely used as refrigerants; whilst they do not deplete the ozone layer, they are potent greenhouse gases (GHG) with high global warming potential (GWP) [26]. With the implementation of the Kigali Amendment to the Montreal Protocol, the phasedown of HFCs is underway [27]. Strategies for eliminating HFCs include the search for low-GWP alternatives [28] and the adoption of natural refrigerants [29]. Proper reclamation and disposal of HFCs at the end of their lifespan are necessary to mitigate their environmental impact [30]. Another main environmental impact stems from the embodied energy consumption and carbon emissions associated with manufacturing integrated systems. This includes the energy required for material extraction, processing, manufacturing, transportation, and the GHG emissions released throughout these phases [31]. García-Sanz-Calcedo et al. [32] quantified the embodied energy and carbon emissions of HVAC systems in

Table 1
Summary of previous LCA studies of HVAC systems.

Ref.	Building type	HVAC systems	Functional unit	Characterisation model	Key finding
[48]	A research lab room with 25.5 m ²	Solar heating ventilating air conditioner based on evaporative cooling and desiccant wheel	Operating for a period of 25 years	Eco-indicator 99	Desiccant wheel system presented larger impacts during the manufacturing phase due to the larger consumption of steel and aluminium
[49]	A test room with 7m ³	Solar HVAC systems with underground water and energy recovery	Operating for 20 years	The carbon footprint	Solar HVAC systems were more efficient in energy usage but contributed more to the material and manufacturing phases
[50]	Residential building with 130 m ²	Solar adsorption chiller and heat pump system	Providing cooling and heating for the building of 10 years	Global energy requirement, GWP	Solar systems showed environmental advantage under a longer lifespan
[51]	A building with peak cooling demand of 12 kW	Solar-assisted space heating and cooling with absorption or adsorption chiller and water storage tanks	Providing heating and cooling for a building with lifespan of 25 years	Global energy requirement, GWP	Installing grid-connected PV had more advantages than stand-alone PV
[52]	An industrial building	Hybrid PV-thermal collectors with thermal storage tanks and air-to-water reversible heat pump	Providing the energy demand of the building	ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint, IPCC GWP 100	Electricity contributed the most to the total impacts, and the proposed system had half of the impacts of the grid-based system
[53]	A residential building with two floors	Grid and PV connected ground and air source heat pumps, natural gas furnace	Operating for one year	ReCiPe Midpoint 2016	Ground source heat pump with PV panel had the lowest emissions at 1242 kg CO ₂ eq./m ²
[54]	Five modular building blocks	Heat pump, mechanical supply and heat recovery ventilation	Operating during the building's lifespan of 60 years	ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint	HVAC systems hardly affected the optimal insulation thickness, but the energy mix had a considerable impact
[55]	An office building	Water-cooled vapor compression chiller	Providing cooling energy for 20 years	ILCD 2011 impact assessment	The environmental performance of the chiller was highly sensitive to the electricity generation mix
[56]	Residential building	Ground source heat pump	Providing space heating and cooling energy in one year	ReCiPe Midpoint and Endpoint 2016	Electricity generation mix with increased use of renewable energy would enhance the technology efficiency and decrease associated emissions
[57]	An academic building	Solar absorption air-conditioning system	Providing cooling energy during the lifespan	TRACI 2.1 method	A reduction of emissions from solar cooling system saved around 80% of the GWP as carbon footprint
[58]	A single-family house	Natural gas furnace, electric air conditioner, and an electric heat pump	The heating and cooling systems designed for the house	GWP 100	The reduction in GHG emissions was primarily due to the changes in the electricity grid mix
Presented study	Group of office buildings	Solar-driven centralised and multi-split HVAC systems, EV charging	Providing heating and cooling energy for 30 years	Environmental Footprint 3.1	The environmental impacts hotspots of the integrated systems

healthcare centres. The analysis revealed that, on average, their embodied energy and carbon emissions per year were 2.65 times and 2.3 times greater than those during the operation phase over a one-year period. These results are significantly influenced by the lifespan of HVAC systems. Therefore, comprehensive assessment of the environmental impact of HVAC systems across their “cradle-to-grave” life cycle is needed to identify possible shifts in environmental burdens across various life cycle phases [33]. Life cycle assessment (LCA) is the most commonly used method for quantifying environmental impact on human health and ecosystem over the entire lifespan of products, goods, and services [34].

Previous studies have applied LCA to support integrated low-carbon energy systems [35], including various aspects such as promoting integrated energy system design [36], effectively utilising renewable energy [37], producing fuel via pyrolysis of polyethylene terephthalate plastic waste [38], in municipal solid waste management [39], and developing sustainable energy technologies [40]. For HVAC systems, LCA has been applied to waste refrigerants recovery [41], the assessment of space heating and cooling systems [33,42], and evaluation of life cycle cost for zero-energy buildings [43]. A comprehensive review identified the environmental burdens of air conditioners at each life cycle stage. It demonstrated that renewable-powered systems can reduce GWP compared to grid-powered systems, but they may also contribute to other environmental issues, such as ecotoxicity, human toxicity, and resource depletion [34]. More LCA studies on HVAC systems in buildings are summarised in Table 1, detailing HVAC systems, functional units, characterisation models applied for impact assessment, and key finding. The main research gaps and the corresponding contributions of

this study are summarised as follows:

- 1) Solar energy has been the most extensively investigated renewable energy source for supporting HVAC systems, offering advantages in efficiency improvement and GHG emission reduction during operation. But most existing studies have not broken down the impacts of specific components within the integrated system, and commonly assume rooftop PV system sized to match the electricity needs of HVAC systems, without considering grid-connected solar PV plant and implication of newly built transmission network. This study carries out a holistic LCA associated with a newly constructed grid-connected solar PV plant which also supplies excess electricity to the grid for other users.
- 2) Previous studies have mostly focused on small thermal zone, such as a single room or an individual building, and lack analyses at the workplace scale. Unlike other building types, office buildings typically have larger floor areas, with HVAC systems that consists of centralised air conditioner (AC) and multi-split AC systems. As office buildings primarily operate during daytime hours, their energy demand aligns well with daily fluctuations in solar radiation, making them well-suited for integration with solar power [44]. This study examines a group of office buildings with complex HVAC configurations integrated with solar energy supply.
- 3) Sensitivity analysis in existing studies is limited to a few parameters such as system lifespan or electricity generation mix which cannot fully reflect the influence of technical variability and interest of stakeholders across different life cycle phases. This study extends the range of parameters to include system weight, rated output power,

Fig. 1. Schematic view of energy supply options to EV chargers and HVAC systems in the pilot site.

heating and cooling performance, EV charging behaviour, and solar irradiance. In addition, the study also considers the disposal of refrigerants, future electricity scenarios, HVAC energy characteristics, and the application of similar integrated systems in office buildings located in different climate zones.

- 4) While there has been growing interest in the environmental analysis of coupled solar-EV charging systems [45–47], limited attention has been paid to the environmental impact of integrated solar-HVAC-EV charging in workplace settings. This study addresses this gap by quantifying the potential environmental benefits of such integrated systems through LCA.

To fill the research gaps identified in existing research, this study conducts a comprehensive LCA of an integrated system comprising EV chargers, HVAC systems, and solar PV plant in a workplace. Unlike previous studies that focus on single building or individual HVAC unit, this study investigates a group of office buildings with centralised and multi-split HVAC systems connected to solar electricity supply. The study also performs a comprehensive sensitivity analysis to assess the influence of critical parameters across all life cycle phases. This study seeks to address the following research questions:

- 1) What are the environmental implications of the integrated systems, and which component and life cycle phase contribute most to these impacts?
- 2) Which key parameters most significantly affect the environmental impacts across the system's life cycle under different electricity supply cases?
- 3) Beyond assessing a specific case, how can the study inform the decarbonisation of workplace energy systems and sustainable energy planning for office buildings with similar operational profiles and climate conditions?

Section 2 presents a system overview of sustainable energy systems for the workplace. Section 3 describes LCA carried out in this study. Section 4 provides results and discussion for the case studies in terms of life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) results, life cycle interpretation, and an extensive sensitivity analysis covering key parameters of stakeholder interest. These include the parameters affecting the manufacturing phase, i.e., the system lifespan and system weight, rated power output, and the parameters relevant to the operation phase, i.e., set point temperatures, heating and cooling durations, the state of charge (SOC) and charging frequency of EV batteries, and solar irradiance. A quantitative evaluation method is used to evaluate how these parameters affect the overall environmental performance of the integrated system. The influence of different refrigerant recycling approaches and alternative electricity generation mixes is also discussed.

2. System overview

In this study, an internal medium-voltage electricity grid supplies power to EV chargers and HVAC systems installed at office buildings located in an industrial district workplace in Port of Sines, Portugal. In addition, a 250-kW solar PV plant constructed on site is considered as an alternative energy supply option, where the electricity generated is prioritised for self-consumption by these systems installed at office buildings. Fig. 1 presents the two energy supply options to EV chargers and HVAC systems evaluated in this study. Detailed descriptions of the EV chargers, HVAC systems, and the solar PV plant are provided in the following subsections, representing inputs for the LCA study.

2.1. Electric vehicle chargers

The electric vehicle charging station at the office building site draws electricity from the grid to charge the batteries of connected EVs. Five EV chargers are installed on site, each with a maximum capacity of 22 kW. A full charging cycle for an EV at 22 kW takes around 2 h and 40 min. Charging generally occurs during working hours (9:00–17:00), although it can be extended if necessary. The actual charging duration depends on the SOC upon arrival at the charging station and the desired SOC at departure. To estimate the annual electricity input to the EVs ($W_{elec,charging}$) and the electricity output from the grid to the chargers ($W_{elec,grid}$), the following equations are applied:

$$W_{elec,charging} = n_{EV} \times (1 - SOC) \times BC_{EV} \times f_{charging} \quad (1)$$

$$W_{elec,grid} = \frac{W_{elec,charging}}{Eff_{charging}} \quad (2)$$

where n_{EV} is the number of EVs, BC_{EV} is the battery capacity of one EV, $f_{charging}$ represents the annual charging frequency per EV, and $Eff_{charging}$ is the charging efficiency of the chargers.

There are 16 EVs used by the office occupants which are charged at the charging station regularly. It is assumed that all EV batteries are homogeneous, each with a capacity of 58 kWh. According to the statistics data [59], EVs with battery capacities exceeding 70 kWh require charging 3 times a week, while those with battery capacities ranging 16–30 kWh charge 4 times weekly. In this study, an average charging frequency of 3 times per week per EV is adopted, resulting in 128 charging sessions annually, based on 300 operational days per year. During charging, a small proportion of electricity is lost, with loss rates ranging 5–15% due to technological limitations of the chargers [60], leading to a charging efficiency of 85–95%.

The optimal SOC range for EV battery operation is recommended to be 20–80% [61]. By assuming a charging efficiency of 95%, the electricity output drawn from the grid to the chargers is estimated, as

Table 2
Estimated electricity output from grid to EV chargers.

SOC when EVs arrive at the charging station (%)	Electricity output from grid to EV chargers (kWh/year)
20	101,352
40	76,014
60	50,676
80	25,338

Table 3
Parameters of HVAC systems installed in the office buildings.

Building	HVAC systems category	Quantity	Maximum capacity (kW)		COP	EER
			Heating	Cooling		
Office Building A	VRV	3	33.5	33.5	4.16	3.63
Office Building B	VRV	1	28	28	4.95	3.92
Office Building C	Multi-split	3	3.2	2.6	3.81	3.80
	Multi-split	8	4.0	3.5	3.61	3.60
	Multi-split	1	5.0	4.6	3.21	3.30
Office Building C	VRV	2	81	73	4.21	4.01
	VRV	2	22	19	3.45	2.84

summarised in Table 2. These values represent the total electricity demand required from the grid to charge the onsite EVs over the course of a year.

2.2. Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems

HVAC systems are currently installed and operated in the three office buildings, each serving distinct functions. Office Building A consists of three floors with a total thermal zone area of 2706.67 m² and is equipped with four external variable refrigerant volume (VRV) systems, split ACs, fans, air-cooled chillers, and an air renewal unit. In addition to the split ACs connected to the rooftop VRV systems, individual AC units are also installed in several rooms. Office Building B, which accommodates the most technical activities, comprises four floors with a total thermal zone area of 2781.65 m². It utilises multi-split HVAC systems connected to various end-user ACs, alongside additional equipment such as fans, an air compressor, and thermal accumulators. Office Building C has three floors with a total thermal zone area of 2511.8 m². On sublevel one, four outdoor VRV units are installed, operating in conjunction with four heat recovery ventilators, of which two located on the ground floor and the others on the first floor. Indoor VRV units are distributed throughout each floor and are connected to the centralised VRV system.

To evaluate the energy consumption of the HVAC systems for producing heating and cooling, the length of the heating and cooling seasons throughout the year is determined based on their set point temperature thresholds. These thresholds indicate the temperatures below or above which heating or cooling is required to maintain indoor comfort [62]. According to the Portuguese regulation on buildings' energy performance, the set point temperatures are set at 18 °C for heating and 25 °C for cooling seasons [63]. Based on historical weather data from Port of Sines [64], the periods when daily temperatures fall below or exceed these set point temperature thresholds correspond to 110 days for heating and 112 days for cooling annually. Heating and cooling operational hours are assumed to be 10 h and 8 h per day, respectively. Using these operational time intervals ($t_{operation}$), the total electricity consumption for heating ($W_{elec.heating}$) and cooling ($W_{elec.cooling}$) through the HVAC systems can be calculated as follows:

$$W_{elec.heating} = \frac{P_{HVAC} \times t_{operation}}{COP} \quad (3)$$

$$W_{elec.cooling} = \frac{P_{HVAC} \times t_{operation}}{EER} \quad (4)$$

Table 4
Monthly electricity consumption of HVAC systems in three office buildings.

Months	Estimated electricity consumption (kWh)		
	Office Building A	Office Building B	Office Building C
Jan	8945	3882	15,370
Feb	7454	3235	12,808
Mar	6242	2678	10,645
Apr	1193	518	2049
May	2586	967	4041
Jun	3622	1167	5178
Jul	6687	2155	9560
Aug	7802	2514	11,153
Sep	6966	2245	9958
Oct	4458	1437	6373
Nov	3578	1553	6148
Dec	4472	1941	7685

where coefficient of performance (COP) and energy efficiency ratio (EER) measure the heating and cooling performance of the HVAC systems, respectively, and P_{HVAC} represents the maximum capacity of the HVAC systems. These parameters are summarised in Table 3. This study focuses on the capacities of the centralised HVAC systems within each building.

Table 4 presents the evaluation of electricity consumption for producing heating and cooling by the HVAC systems, derived from set point temperatures and degree-days. HVAC systems have considerable variability in electricity consumption across different office buildings. The estimated figures represent the electricity required to provide heating and cooling at the maximum capacity of the HVAC systems. The corresponding delivered heating and cooling energy, derived from the estimated electricity consumption, is shown in Fig. 2.

2.3. Solar PV plant

A distributed solar PV plant with an installed capacity of 250 kW is connected to the office building site. A field of PV panels generates renewable electricity intended to support the operation of EV chargers and HVAC systems. The specifications of single PV panel are summarised in Table 5.

Based on the installed power output (250 kW), the total area required for the solar PV panels (A_{PV}) is calculated as follows [66]:

$$P_{PV} = A_{PV} \times Irr \times Eff_{PV} \quad (5)$$

where P_{PV} is the power output, Irr is solar irradiance, and Eff_{PV} is the module efficiency. The PV plant is equipped with 15 inverters, each with a maximum DC power input of 17.41 kW and a rated alternating current power output of 17 kW. The inverters convert the DC output from the PV system into alternating current power, which is then supplied to the electricity transmission network. The real-time active power output from the inverters is shown in Fig. 3. The total annual power generation of the PV plant amounts to 403.6 MWh.

2.4. Electricity generation mix

Fig. 4 shows electricity generation mix in Portugal in 2023, highlighting the energy sources that contribute to the grid electricity supply. Current electricity generation in Portugal has undergone a significant transition towards renewable energy sources. Around 75% of electricity is now generated from renewable sources, particularly from wind and hydro power. Although solar energy currently accounts for a relatively small share of electricity generation, it holds considerable potential for future expansion.

3. Life cycle assessment (LCA)

In accordance with ISO 14040 [68] and ISO 14044 [69] standards,

Fig. 2. Monthly delivered energy from HVAC systems in three office buildings.

Table 5
Specifications of a PV panel.

PV panel module	ReneSola JC255M-24/Bb [65]
Weight	18.5 kg
Length	1640 mm
Width	992 mm
Thickness	40 mm
Solar irradiance	1000 W/m ²
Module efficiency	15.7%

LCA carried out in this study comprises four phases: goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory analysis (LCI), LCIA, and life cycle interpretation. This section outlines the first three phases, with the final phase presented in the subsequent section.

3.1. Goal and scope definition

The reason of conducting this LCA study is to systematically evaluate and quantify the environmental impacts of EV chargers and HVAC systems at office building sites under different electricity supply scenarios, which is the interest of the site operator. This LCA study identifies significant impact categories associated with these energy systems throughout their full life cycle phases. The intended application is to inform improvements in system operations and future system development aimed at reducing environmental impacts. Two cases were defined to compare the environmental implications of electricity supply sources:

- Baseline case: EV chargers and HVAC systems consume electricity supplied by the national grid.
- Alternative case: EV chargers and HVAC systems are powered by a 250-kW onsite solar PV plant.

As such, the EV chargers, HVAC systems, solar PV plant, transmission

network, and grid electricity together constitute the integrated energy systems in the pilot site, i.e., the product system assessed in this study. The function of this product system is to generate and supply energy to the pilot sites for EV and HVAC systems operation for mobility, heating, and cooling. The functional unit is defined as the operation of these energy systems at office building sites over 30 years. To reflect the varying lifespans of individual components, their replacement, if relevant, is included within the scope of the study.

The system boundary defined for both cases is illustrated in Fig. 5. Within this boundary, each energy component is modelled according to its elementary input and output flows at every life cycle phase. This study adopts a comprehensive “cradle-to-grave” approach, covering raw material acquisition, construction and manufacturing, operation and maintenance, and end-of-life treatment. Several assumptions are consistently applied across both cases:

Fig. 4. Electricity generation mix in Portugal in 2023 [67].

Fig. 3. Active power output from inverters.

Fig. 5. System boundaries of this LCA study.

Table 6
Data sources of LCI for manufacturing energy systems.

Component	Data sources	Location	Size/ capacity of the system in the data sources	Size/ capacity of the system in this study
Fan	Fan production, for power supply unit [70]	Europe	1 kg	178.6 kg
Air conditioner	Residential air conditioning [71]	Saudi Arabia	1 kg	8321.5 kg
Ventilation	Blower and heat exchange unit production, central, 600–1200 m ³ /h [70]	Europe	143 kg	89.2 kg
EV charger	Charger production, for electric passenger car [70]	Global	1 kg	275 kg
PV module	Market for photovoltaic panel, multi-Si wafer [70]	Global	1 m ²	1789.6 m ²
PV mounting structure	PV mounting structure, for 570kWp open ground module [70]	Global	1 m ²	1562.5 m ²
Inverter	Market for inverter, 2.5 kW [70]	Global	2.5 kW	17 kW
PV electric installation	PV, electric installation for 570kWp module, open ground [70]	Global	570 kW	250 kW
Transmission network	Transmission network construction, electricity, medium voltage [70]	Switzerland	1 km	0.23 km
Grid electricity	Market for electricity, medium voltage [70]	Portugal	1 kWh	1 kWh

- (1) The SOC of EVs upon arrival at the charging station is assumed to be 20%.
- (2) HVAC systems operate 10 h and 8 h per day to provide heating and cooling respectively.

- (3) The lifespans of EV chargers, HVAC systems, and solar PV plant are assumed as 15, 15, and 30 years, respectively.
- (4) A constant solar irradiance of 1000 W/m² is considered.
- (5) The material composition of HVAC systems remains consistent across different brands and models, with variations only in their weights per unit.
- (6) No replacement and dismantling of the solar PV plant is planned for the entire operational phase.
- (7) Maintenance of the transmission network over its 30-year lifespan is included.
- (8) Transportation between life cycle phases is not explicitly modelled, as transportation data is already embedded in the process data adopted in this study.
- (9) Non-recyclable plastics generated during the end-of-life process are disposed of through landfill and incineration, 50% each.

3.2. Life cycle inventory analysis (LCI)

During LCI, all input and output data are compiled to quantify the materials and energy consumed, as well as emissions released by the product system at each life cycle stage. Table 6 summarises the data sources used for the various components, with the majority derived from Ecoinvent 3.10 [70] commercial database. Inventory data are adjusted using scaling factors that correspond to the actual size and capacity of the product system. For instance, the LCI dataset for ACs is provided per unit mass (i.e., 1 kg). Thus the input and output data of ACs in this study are estimated by multiplying their total weight by the respective inventory values per unit mass. Similarly, the inventory data for a 570-kW

Table 7
Operation and maintenance data of the product system.

Operation phase	Input and output
HVAC systems in Office Building A	0.25 kWh electricity used to produce 1 kWh heating and cooling energy
HVAC systems in Office Building B	0.28 kWh electricity used to produce 1 kWh heating and cooling energy
HVAC systems in Office Building C	0.26 kWh electricity used to produce 1 kWh heating and cooling energy
EV chargers	1.05 kWh electricity used to charge 1 kWh electricity to EVs
Solar PV plant	1.07 kWh solar energy and 2.13×10^{-5} kg tap water used to produce 1 kWh electricity
Transmission network operation	0.005 kWh electricity and 1.13×10^{-7} kg sulphur hexafluoride used to transmit 1 kWh electricity
Electricity grid operation	0.037 kWh electricity used to import 1 kWh electricity
Transmission network maintenance	935 MJ diesel, 0.875 kg lubricating oil, 0.065 kg cement, 0.6 kg steel, and 5.2 kg zinc used to maintain 1 km transmission network per year

Table 8
Mass and disposal processes applied to waste in this study.

Waste	End-of-life treatment process	Mass (kg)
Aluminium scrap	Aluminium is sorted from the residual, yielding distinct fractions for aluminium recovery and recycling	1382
Waste copper	Pure, isolated copper is recycled directly. The copper in waste is recycled from bottom ash of the incineration	2916
Waste steel	Pure, isolated steel is recycled directly rather than going to incinerator. Scrap steel in the waste is recycled from bottom ash of the incineration	7469
Waste plastic	Waste plastic is transported to the recycling facility where it is sorted, cleaned, and subsequently ground into flakes for recycling. The non-recyclable fraction of the plastic is disposed of by sending half to landfill and half to incinerator	5308
Waste rubber	The waste rubber is disposed in the incineration plant with flue gas cleaning	29
Used refrigerants	Used refrigerants are recycled, purified, and finally recharged to the machine	289
Municipal waste	The non-recyclable municipal waste is disposed in the incineration plant	143
Zinc scrap	Pure, isolated zinc is recycled directly. Zinc scrap in the waste is recycled from bottom ash of the incineration	8.56
Scrap printed wiring boards	Used printed wiring boards are weighted, shredded, and sampled at a preparation plant	72
Electronics scrap	The electronics scrap is dismantled to separate iron scrap, plastics, used cable and scrip printed wiring boards. Metal parts are recycled, plastic parts are incinerated, and the remaining materials are disposed for further recycling	0.75
Waste mineral wool	The waste mineral wool is sorted and crushed in the dry sorting plant for further recycling	0.19
Used capacitor	Used capacitor is disposed as hazardous waste in the incineration plant	31

solar PV plant is proportionally scaled to represent a 250-kW plant. The production of EV chargers is based on a dataset representing a unit used to charge the Li-ion battery of an electric passenger car. HVAC systems are composed of components such as fans, ACs, and ventilation units, with manufacturing processes involving metal casting, plastics moulding, sheet rolling, and wire drawing. The construction of the solar PV plant covers installation of the mounting structure, electrical devices, PV modules, inverters, and a transmission network. An additional transmission line is constructed to feed the electricity generated by the solar PV plant to the grid. Manufacturing data for grid electricity also includes the infrastructure needed for electricity generation.

The operation of the product system primarily depends on electricity, alongside material inputs such as tap water for cleaning solar PV panels, as well as diesel, lubricating oil, cement, steel, and zinc for maintaining the transmission network. Table 7 presents the input energy and material requirements per unit of output during the operation phase. To transmit 1 kWh of electricity from the solar PV plant to end users, 1.13×10^{-7} kg of sulphur hexafluoride and 0.005 kWh of electricity are required to maintain the transmission network infrastructure whereas importing 1 kWh of electricity through the grid requires 0.037 kWh of electricity for transformer operation.

Given the 15-year lifespan of HVAC systems and EV chargers, each is replaced once in year 15. All discarded devices undergo disassembly and end-of-life treatment, including recycling, landfill, and incineration. The resulting waste materials include metallic scrap, plastic waste, used refrigerant, and other solid residues. The mass of these waste fractions are derived based on the proportion of each material relative to the total component weight, with life cycle data for disposal processes sources from Ecoinvent 3.10 [70]. Table 8 details the mass of various waste streams and their associated disposal methods. Whilst pure metals are directly recycled, compound metallic scrap is recovered from the bottom ash of incineration. Used refrigerant is reclaimed following discharge

* The amounts on the y-axis are presented on a logarithmic scale

Fig. 6. Materials used in manufacturing the product system i.e., integrated energy systems in the pilot site.

and purification. Non-recyclable plastics are disposed of through landfill and incineration.

3.3. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) methodology

During LCIA, resource consumption and emissions compiled during the LCI phase are classified into defined impact categories and subsequently characterised into impact scores (s_i), also referred to as indicator results or LCIA results. This characterisation is performed using the characterisation factors (CF), as expressed by the following Eq. [72]:

$$s_i = \sum (M_k \times CF_{i,k}) \quad (6)$$

where M_k represents the mass of substance k consumed or emitted across the life cycle phases, and $CF_{i,k}$ is the CF of substance k in relation to impact category i . Therefore, the impact score of impact category i (s_i) is calculated by summing the products of each substance's mass and its corresponding CF .

Impact categories are defined differently by various characterisation models, incorporating relevant characterisation factors. This study applies the Environmental Footprint (EF 3.1) characterisation model [73], which is maintained by the European Commission, employing a midpoint approach to assess 16 impact categories. This characterisation model has been selected for its relevance to the European context, ensuring alignment with the pilot site.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) results

As presented in Fig. 6, materials used in manufacturing the product system in this study can be categorised as non-renewable and renewable resources, with consumption ranging 3–5 orders of magnitude for individual components. Due to the large differences in orders of magnitude among the results, the amounts on the y-axis in Fig. 6 are presented on a logarithmic scale instead of a linear scale to improve results comparability. The corresponding absolute values are provided in Supplementary Information Table S.1. In the non-renewable category, the most consumed resources include gangue, gravel, calcite, shale, and sand, whereas carbon dioxide, nitrogen, oxygen, and wood dominate the renewable resources. These resources represent raw materials exploited from nature environment, which are subsequently processed for use in the manufacturing phase. The construction of grid electricity infrastructures consumes 2.37×10^5 kg and 1.01×10^4 kg non-renewable and renewable resources, respectively, which relies substantially on

Fig. 7. Emissions of the baseline and alternative cases during the operation phase: (a) to freshwater and air; and (b) breakdown of air emissions.

Fig. 8. Contributions towards individual impacts of: (a) baseline and (b) alternative cases.

natural resource extraction and can result in the highest potential impacts to the environment due to resource depletion.

The LCI results for emissions during the operation phase associated with the baseline and alternative cases are compared in Fig. 7 using a logarithmic scale, with the corresponding absolute values provided in Supplementary Information Table S.2 and Table S.3. As shown in Fig. 7 (a), emissions are released into air and freshwater, comprising inorganic emissions, organic emissions and particulate matters. Among all,

inorganic emissions dominate the total emissions to air, contributing 2.99×10^7 kg and 1.38×10^5 kg for baseline and alternative cases, respectively. The highest proportion of these inorganic emissions is attributed to CO₂, followed by CH₄, volatile organic compounds (VOC), CO, NO_x, and SO₂, as illustrated in Fig. 7(b). The comparison demonstrates that the alternative case where electricity is supplied by the solar PV plant significantly reduces the release of environmental pollutants. For solar PV-supplied electricity, the primary source of emissions arises

Table 9

Electricity production and reduction of fossil resources resulting from incineration treatment.

Waste to be incinerated	Electricity generated (MJ)	Avoided fossil fuel consumption (MJ)
Solid waste from HVAC systems in Office Building A	13,695	19,268
Solid waste from HVAC systems in Office Building B	13,325	19,091
Solid waste from HVAC systems in Office Building C	11,816	17,859
Solid waste from EV chargers	555	417

from the operation and maintenance of the transmission network.

4.2. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) results and life cycle interpretation

Fig. 8 illustrates the contributions of different components at relevant life cycle phases to specific impact categories for (a) the baseline and (b) alternative cases. In Fig. 8(a), the manufacturing and operation phases associated with the grid are the predominant contributors to most impact categories, except for ozone depletion. The construction of grid electricity infrastructure, including generation units and the transmission network, has a greater impact on water use, land use, human toxicity, and freshwater eutrophication than the manufacturing of HVAC systems and EV chargers. This means that installing renewable electricity generation facilities which often require large areas of open land is associated with substantial water consumption and land occupation. The operation of HVAC systems and EV chargers is largely dependent on electricity supplied by the national grid, which is generated from a mix of energy sources. Therefore, increased electricity demand from HVAC systems and EV chargers amplifies the impacts associated with the operation phase. As approximately 24% of electricity in Portugal is still generated from fossil-based power plants, there are notable contributions to impact categories such as climate change, fossil resources consumption, photochemical ozone formation, particulate matter formation, eutrophication, and acidification. Although the manufacturing of HVAC systems represents the largest share of ozone

depletion, which is measured in CFC-11 equivalent, the magnitude of this impact is less than 1 kg CFC-11 equivalent. This demonstrates that the current usage of HFCs as refrigerants, in place of chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), has significantly reduced the potential of ozone layer depletion.

In Fig. 8(b), the distribution of impacts for the alternative case presents a notable shift compared to the baseline case. The impacts associated with the manufacturing phase become more dominant relative to those from the operation phase. In particular, the installation of the solar PV plant significantly increases both water and land use. Meanwhile, the construction of the transmission network required for delivering electricity from the solar PV system to end users has a pronounced effect on mineral and metal resources consumption as well as non-cancer human toxicity. Despite the operation phase of HVAC systems and EV chargers powered by the solar PV plant contributes negligible environmental impacts, the impacts associated with the construction of the solar PV plant and transmission network remain critical.

As shown in Fig. 8, the environmental impacts from the end-of-life treatment of discarded HVAC systems and EV chargers are relatively minor compared to those from the manufacturing and operation phases. Most impact categories remain low in magnitude, apart from freshwater ecotoxicity, ionising radiation on human health, land use, and water use (which are 2–3 orders of magnitude, primarily resulting from landfill disposal). Additionally, incinerating waste offers the potential to offset fossil resource consumption by generating electricity during the process, thereby avoiding the equivalent use of fossil fuels, as indicated in Table 9 based on the LCA model results. Among all, the solid waste from the HVAC systems in Office Building A provides the greatest environmental benefit through reduced fossil fuel consumption.

Fig. 9 compares the LCIA results of both cases across 12 impact categories shown on a logarithmic scale, while the corresponding absolute values are provided in Supplementary Information Table S.4. For human toxicity (non-cancer and cancer), ozone depletion, and particulate matter formation, with values below 1, are not displayed in the figure. The baseline case exhibits higher burdens in all presented impact categories compared to the alternative case. The most substantial reduction of environmental impact is observed in climate change, where emissions decrease by 87.28% from 1.74×10^6 kg CO₂ equivalent in the

* The impact results on the y-axis are presented on a logarithmic scale

Fig. 9. The LCIA results for the operation phase. (AC: acidification. CC: climate change. ETF: ecotoxicity, freshwater. EPF: eutrophication, freshwater. EPM: eutrophication, marine. EPT: eutrophication, terrestrial. IR: ionising radiation, human health. LU: land use. PF: photochemical ozone formation, human health. RUF: resource use, fossils. RUM: resource use, mineral and metals. WU: water use.)

Table 10
Key parameters for sensitivity analysis.

Key parameter	Component	Influence phase	Baseline value	Reference
System lifespan	HVAC systems	Manufacturing	15 years	[34]
System weight	EV chargers	Manufacturing	15 years	[74]
	HVAC systems	Manufacturing	8589.3 kg	System design
Rated output power	EV chargers	Manufacturing	55 kg each	[75]
	Solar PV plant	Manufacturing	250 kW	System design
Heating set point temperature	HVAC systems	Operation	18 °C	[63]
Cooling set point temperature	HVAC systems	Operation	25 °C	[63]
Daily heating duration	HVAC systems	Operation	10 h	[76]
Daily cooling duration	HVAC systems	Operation	8 h	[76]
SOC of EVs upon arrival for charging	EV chargers	Operation	0.2	[61]
Weekly charging frequency of one EV	EV chargers	Operation	3 times	[59]
Solar irradiance	Solar PV plant	Operation	1000 W/m ²	[65]

baseline case to 2.22×10^5 kg CO₂ equivalent in the alternative case. This reduction is primarily attributable to the elimination of fossil fuel consumption in electricity generation. Meanwhile, reductions exceeding

80% are also observed in acidification, marine and terrestrial eutrophication, photochemical ozone formation, and fossil resource use. It is indicated that significant improvement in overall environmental performance by the solar PV plant. The smallest reduction is seen in the use of mineral and metal resources, with a decrease of just 4.03% from 12.96 kg Sb equivalent to 12.44 kg Sb equivalent. The limited reduction is due to the depletion of the mineral and metals resources primarily originating from the manufacturing phase of the product system. Both cases show notable impacts in land use, which relates to potential losses in soil filtration capacity, biodiversity, and accelerated transformation of land functions. These findings underscore the long-term environmental sustainability, and the need to manage land occupation carefully, even in low-emission operation.

4.3. Sensitivity analysis

The notable environmental burdens have shown from manufacturing EV chargers and HVAC systems, constructing the solar PV plant, and operating EV chargers and HVAC systems supplied by grid electricity. Therefore a sensitivity analysis was conducted to examine the effects of key parameters on the LCIA results based on the technical variability, and interest of stakeholders, particularly the site operator and building occupants. These parameters and their corresponding baseline values are listed in Table 10. Additional LCIA was carried out by varying these parameters by $\pm 10\%$ – $\pm 30\%$, except for the heating and cooling set point temperatures, to assess changes in LCIA results compared to the results of the baseline and alternative cases. All the results from the sensitivity analysis are presented in Supplementary Information

Fig. 10. Changes in LCIA results compared to the baseline case when varying system lifespan of: (a) HVAC systems and (b) EV chargers, and compared to alternative case when varying lifespan of: (c) HVAC systems and (d) EV chargers.

Impact categories

AC: Acidification; CC: Climate Change; ETF: Ecotoxicity, freshwater; EPF: Eutrophication, freshwater; EPM: Eutrophication, marine; EPT: Eutrophication, terrestrial; HTC: Human toxicity, cancer; HTN: Human toxicity, non-cancer; IR: Ionising radiation, human health; LU: Land use; OD: Ozone depletion; PM: Particulate matter; PF: Photochemical ozone formation, human health; RUF: Resource use, fossils; RUM: Resource use, mineral and metals; WU: Water use

Fig. 11. Changes in LCIA results compared to the baseline case when varying weight of: (a) HVAC systems and (b) EV chargers, and compared to alternative case when varying weight of: (c) HVAC systems and (d) EV chargers.

Tables S.5–S.26.

In practice, the operational lifespan of the product system is closely related to its maintenance cost. Premature failure or inefficient use can result in shorter lifespan, which potentially lead to more frequent replacements and increased demand for material and energy during the manufacturing phase. For HVAC systems, the lifespan commonly ranges from 10 to 30 years [34], therefore a baseline value of 15 years is assumed. Similarly, the lifespan of EV chargers is reported to range from 10 to 20 years [74], and a 15-year lifespan is adopted as baseline value. Fig. 10 illustrates the changes in LCIA results when the lifespan of HVAC systems and EV chargers varies from 19.5 years (+30%) to 10.5 years (−30%). It is found that extending the lifespan reduces environmental impacts compared to both cases, whereas shorter lifespan significantly increases the LCIA results since more frequent replacements of HVAC systems and EV chargers during the operational period are needed. The most substantial rises compared to the baseline case observed in Figs. 10(a) and 10(b) are ozone depletion (34.45%) for HVAC systems, and the use of mineral and metal resources (9.2%) for EV chargers. These are primarily due to the manufacturing phase of HVAC systems, during which the use of HFCs as refrigerants dominates the ozone depletion impact. For EV chargers, the use of aluminium, iron, nickel, and other elements contribute mostly to the use of mineral and metal resources. A 30% less lifespan of HVAC systems also leads to notable increases in mineral and metal resources (7.63%), cancer human toxicity (7.46%), and freshwater eutrophication (6.25%). And significant rises are found in freshwater eutrophication (3.15%), non-cancer human toxicity (2.97), and freshwater ecotoxicity (2.26%) for EV chargers. Phosphorus, used as a dopant in electronic devices which constitute the core device of

HVAC systems and EV chargers, is closely linked to freshwater eutrophication. In Figs. 10(c) and 10(d) where the changes are relative to alternative case, a larger increase in LCIA results are revealed with shorter lifespan. The ranges of change expand to 40.97% to −22.06% in ozone depletion for HVAC systems and to 9.6% to −5.17% in the use of mineral and metal resources for EV chargers. This demonstrates that the lifespan as a parameter mainly attributed to the manufacturing phase influences the product system more when electricity is supplied by the solar PV plant.

System weight of the product system is closely associated with the materials used in manufacturing phase, and its reduction has been shown to improve environmental performance [48]. The total system weight of HVAC systems comprises 178.6 kg of fans, 8321.5 kg of ACs, and 89.2 kg of ventilation unit, as shown in Table 6. For the EV chargers, a weight of 55 kg per unit was adopted based on the manufacturer's manual [75], with a total of five chargers built on site. As shown in Fig. 11, when weight of HVAC systems and EV chargers increases by 30% to 11,166 kg and 357 kg, respectively, the environmental impacts reach the maximal values. Conversely, decreasing weight of HVAC system to 6012 kg and EV chargers to 192 kg leads to the largest decrement in these impacts. The changes in LCIA results display a linear relationship with each 10% variation in system weight, resulting in larger impacts in the heavier HVAC systems than those of the EV chargers. Figs. 11(a) and 11(b) show again that the most pronounced rises are in ozone depletion (24.12%) for HVAC systems and in the use of mineral and metal resources (6.45%) for EV chargers when compared to the baseline case. Similarly, Figs. 11(c) and 11(d) indicate that the system weight affects more when product system's electricity is supplied

Fig. 12. Changes in LCIA results compared to the baseline case when varying set point temperature of HVAC systems for: (a) heating and (b) cooling, and compared to alternative case when varying set point temperature of HVAC systems for: (c) heating and (d) cooling.

by solar PV system, with the most increases of 28.68% in ozone depletion and 6.72% in the use of mineral and metal resources for HVAC systems and EV chargers, respectively. These results are consistent with the contribution analysis in Fig. 8, showing that the LCIA results of alternative case are more relative to the manufacturing phase.

Set point temperature controls HVAC systems switching on and off, determining their electricity consumption. In this study, the heating and cooling set point temperatures are set at 18 °C and 25 °C, respectively, according to Portuguese regulation on buildings' energy performance [62,63]. A $\pm 30\%$ change in the set point temperatures would result in extreme temperatures that fall outside thermal comfort range. For example, during the winter period from November to March in Ports of Sines, the daily average outdoor temperature exceeds 23.4 °C (+30% of 18 °C) on only one day based on historical weather data [64]. If this value was adopted as the heating set point, the HVAC would operate continuously throughout the entire heating season. Conversely, the daily average temperature falls below 12.6 °C (−30% of 18 °C) on only 15 days during winter. Using this value as the heating set point temperature would result in little heating demand for most of time. A similar situation applies to the summer. Only 11 days have average temperatures higher than 32.5 °C (+30% of 25 °C), and almost all days exceed 17.5 °C (−30% of 25 °C), if either of these extreme values are set as the cooling set point temperatures, the resulting HVAC cooling operation would be non-representative of realistic building operation. Therefore, the variation range of the heating and cooling set point temperatures are limited to $\pm 20\%$, ranging from 14.4 °C–21.6 °C for heating and from 20 °C–30 °C for cooling, to ensure a realistic HVAC operation conditions.

The results in Fig. 12 illustrate that heating set points exhibit an

opposite effect on the changes in LCIA results compared to cooling set points. This is because a higher heating set point increases the possibility of indoor temperature being below the set point, resulting in longer daily heating duration for the HVAC systems. In contrast, a cooling set point requires indoor temperature to exceed this threshold to activate cooling from HVAC systems, therefore increased cooling set point decreases probability of cooling. Figs. 12(a) and 12(b) show that when the heating and cooling set points are set to 21.6 °C (+20%) and 20 °C (−20%), respectively, the most substantial increases are observed both in land use, which reach 27.24% and 26.15% above the baseline case. When the heating and cooling set points are reduced to 14.4 °C (−20%) and raised to 30 °C (+20%), the impacts of land use are maximumly reduced by 25.32% and 23.79%, respectively. This suggests that heating set points affect more on environmental impacts than cooling set points, mostly due to the higher electricity consumption associated with heating. The minimum changes in LCIA results are found in ozone depletion which is primarily relative to the manufacturing phase of HVAC systems. Compared to alternative case, land use increases the most by 26.85% and 25.77% when heating set point is increased by 20% and cooling set point is decreased by 20%, respectively, as shown in Fig. 12(c) and 12(d). The effects of set points on changes in LCIA results are smaller in alternative case, which reflects that impacts from operation phase are reduced when the electricity supply is supplied by solar PV system. Although adjusting set point temperatures can reduce LCIA results, excessively low heating temperature or high cooling temperature will compromise occupants' comfort in the room. Dynamic control of set point temperatures could be introduced to balance reductions in environmental impacts and indoor comfort.

Impact categories

AC: Acidification; CC: Climate Change; ETF: Ecotoxicity, freshwater; EPF: Eutrophication, freshwater; EPM: Eutrophication, marine; EPT: Eutrophication, terrestrial; HTC: Human toxicity, cancer; HTN: Human toxicity, non-cancer; IR: Ionising radiation, human health; LU: Land use; OD: Ozone depletion; PM: Particulate matter; PF: Photochemical ozone formation, human health; RUF: Resource use, fossils; RUM: Resource use, mineral and metals; WU: Water use

Fig. 13. Changes in LCIA results compared to the baseline case when varying daily durations of HVAC systems for: (a) heating and (b) cooling, and compared to alternative case when varying daily durations of HVAC systems for: (c) heating and (d) cooling.

Electricity consumption during the operation phase of HVAC systems is also closely linked to the daily heating and cooling duration. Based on the regular operating hours of office building in Portugal [76], the daily heating and cooling durations are assumed as 10 h and 8 h, respectively. With $\pm 30\%$ variations in daily heating and cooling durations, the daily heating hours range from 7 to 13 h, while the daily cooling hours range from 5.60 to 10.4 h. The results shown in Fig. 13 indicate that environmental impacts increase across all impact categories due to the extended operational periods and decrease when these periods are shortened, exhibiting a linear relationship with variations in operational hours. The changes in LCIA results compared to the baseline case are shown in Fig. 13(a) and 13(b). Notably, heating durations present more significant effect on LCIA results than cooling durations, primarily due to more electricity consumption for heating. The most pronounced change is also observed in land use, varying by $\pm 10.57\%$ and $\pm 8.78\%$ for 30% prolonged or less heating and cooling durations, respectively. The least pronounced change is observed in ozone depletion which proves that this impact is primarily associated with the manufacturing phase of HVAC systems. The reductions of 5.85×10^4 kg CO₂ equivalent emissions and 8.49×10^5 MJ fossil resources from one hour less of heating, and 6.08×10^4 kg CO₂ equivalent emissions and 8.82×10^5 MJ fossil resources from one hour less cooling, demonstrate a substantial potential for emission reduction through more efficient HVAC systems operation. In Fig. 13(c) and 13(d) where the LCIA results are compared to alternative case, the changes vary by $\pm 10.42\%$ and $\pm 8.66\%$ for 30% prolonged or shorter heating and cooling durations, respectively,

indicating a less effect of heating and cooling duration on the alternative case.

To investigate the influence of key parameters related to EV chargers, the SOC of EV batteries upon arrival at charging stations and weekly charging frequency of EVs are considered, as shown in Fig. 14. The baseline SOC is defined as the minimum value within the recommended range [61], whereas the charging frequency is assumed as 3 times per week based on the battery capacities [59]. With $\pm 30\%$ changes in SOC, the SOC levels range from 14%–26%. Figs. 14(a) and 14(b) indicate that the environmental impacts decrease as SOC increases. Higher SOC levels lower charging demand, resulting in less electricity being drawn from the grid. The findings show that a 10%–30% increase in SOC could reduce impact the most in land use by 0.87%–2.59% in the baseline case and 0.85%–2.56% in alternative cases. The slightest change is observed in ozone depletion, similar to the effects of other operating parameters for HVAC systems. Figs. 14(c) and 14(d) present the effect of weekly charging frequency of EVs on LCIA results, which reveals increased trends of all environmental impacts with more frequent charging. The most significant changes in LCIA results are found in land use with increases in 10.38% and 10.23% compared to the baseline case and alternative case, respectively. As the battery performance is closely related to both the SOC of EV batteries and charging frequency, proper battery management essentially affects the environmental impacts associated with the electricity consumption during the operation of EV chargers.

Fig. 15 illustrates the changes in LCIA results resulting from varying

Impact categories

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Fig. 14. Changes in LCIA results when varying the SOC of EV batteries compared to: (a) baseline case and (b) alternative case, and changes in LCIA results when varying weekly charging frequency of EVs compared to: (c) baseline case and (d) alternative case.

rated output power of solar PV plant and solar irradiance during the operation phase. Compared to the alternative case, Figs. 15(a)–15(c) show that while increasing rated power can reduce all environmental impacts, the magnitude of these changes is minimal. The largest change is found in the use of mineral and metal resources with only a 0.37% reduction when the rated output power is increased by 30% to 325 kW. This reflects that when the electricity demand of the HVAC systems and EV chargers is far below the full capacity of solar PV plant, the effect of rated output power on the environmental impacts is negligible. Figs. 15 (d)–15(f) show the changes in LCIA results when solar irradiance varies from 700 W/m² to 1300 W/m². It is found that lower solar irradiance levels lead to higher environmental impacts, as reflected in the LCIA results. This is due to lower solar irradiance causes insufficient electricity supply from the solar PV plant which potentially results in larger panel areas and a greater number of panels. And at last it leads to higher contribution from the manufacturing phase of the solar PV plant to total LCIA results. The most substantial increase is observed in land use, which rises by nearly 40% when solar irradiance drops to 700 W/m². CO₂ emissions and fossil resource use increase by 4.95%–18.49% and 4.77%–17.84%, respectively, as solar irradiance decreases from 1000 W/m² to 700 W/m². These findings suggest that constructing solar PV plants in low-irradiance locations may be environmentally unviable, as the increased environmental impacts during construction could outweigh the zero-emission benefits during operation.

To summarise the effects of key parameters on the reductions in LCIA results, Fig. 16 illustrates the magnitude of the maximum reduction achieved by controlling values of each parameter. Fig. 16(a) shows that

environmental impacts can be mitigated the most by reducing set point temperature for heating, followed by increasing set point temperature for cooling. One exception is observed in ozone depletion which is effectively reduced by reducing system weight and extending system lifespan of HVAC systems. Other strategies such as reducing heating and cooling duration of HVAC systems and reducing charging frequency of EVs also present noteworthy reduction effects in LCIA results, ranging from 1.7%–10.6%. In Fig. 16(b) which compares reductions in LCIA results to alternative case, the most significant reduction effects are also achieved by adjusting heating and cooling set point temperatures. Extending system lifespan and reducing system weight of HVAC systems, and increasing solar irradiance show comparable reduction effects in LCIA results.

4.4. Further discussion

Although the results presented above indicate that ozone layer depletion from HVAC systems is relatively low, the use of HFCs as refrigerants still presents significant global warming potential. In both the baseline and alternative cases, the reclamation of used refrigerants following the disassembly of discarded HVAC systems was considered. Refrigerants at the end of their life are typically managed through one of three routes: venting, reclamation, and final disposal by incineration. Using GWP values relative to CO₂ from the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC AR6) [77] and the life cycle inventory data for refrigerant disposal obtained from the Ecoinvent process “treatment of used refrigerant R134a” [70], the GWP

Impact categories

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Fig. 15. Changes in contribution from the solar PV plant compared to alternative case when rated output power of solar PV plant is varied with: (a) ±30%, (b) ±20%, (c) ±10%, and changes compared to alternative case when solar irradiance is varied with: (d) ±30%, (e) ±20%, (f) ±10%.

Impact categories

AC: Acidification; CC: Climate Change; ETF: Ecotoxicity, freshwater; EPF: Ecotoxicity, freshwater; EPM: Eutrophication, marine; EPT: Eutrophication, terrestrial; HTC: Human toxicity, cancer; HTN: Human toxicity, non-cancer; IR: Ionising radiation, human health; LU: Land use; OD: Ozone depletion; PM: Particulate matter; PF: Photochemical ozone formation, human health; RUF: Resource use, fossils; RUM: Resource use, mineral and metals; WU: Water use

Strategies for reducing environmental impacts

I: Extending system lifespan (HVAC systems); II: Extending system lifespan (EV chargers); III: Reducing system weight (HVAC systems); IV: Reducing system weight (EV chargers); V: Reducing set point temperature for heating; VI: Increasing set point temperature for cooling; VII: Reducing heating duration per day; VIII: Reducing cooling duration per day; IX: Increasing SOC; X: Reducing charging frequency per week; XI: Increasing rated output power of solar PV plant; XII: Increasing solar irradiance

Fig. 16. Magnitude of reduction in LCIA results compared to: (a) baseline case and (b) alternative case.

Table 11

Comparison of the GWP 100 of disposing used refrigerant and production of refrigerant.

Process	GWP 100 (kg CO ₂ equivalent)
Production of refrigerant	5385
Reclamation of used refrigerant	583
Disposing used refrigerant in incineration	1298
Venting refrigerant	491,436

over a 100-year horizon (GWP 100) associated with the three end-of-life routes and the production of new refrigerant is assessed, as summarised in Table 11. A total of 321 kg of used refrigerant is recovered from discarded HVAC systems across three office buildings. Manufacturing

HVAC systems results in a GWP 100 of 83,430 kg CO₂ equivalent by using entirely newly produced refrigerants. When the newly produced refrigerant is substituted with reclaimed refrigerant, the GWP 100 is decreased by 5.8% to 78,628 kg CO₂ equivalent. Meanwhile, raw materials used in producing HFCs refrigerant such as hydrogen fluoride can be substantially conserved. Of the evaluated processes, refrigerant reclamation shows the lowest GWP 100, which is more than twice as low as incineration. Direct venting of refrigerant, by contrast, results in a GWP 100 nearly 100 times greater than that of producing new refrigerant. While this study does not assess specific reclamation technologies, the GWP 100 values in Table 11 align closely with the results in Ref. [25], which presents a GWP 100 of over 600 kg CO₂ equivalent for refrigerant reclamation. These findings underscore the significant environmental benefits of recovering and reusing refrigerant in

Fig. 17. GHG emissions from the product system when varying COP and EER for: (a) baseline case and (b) alternative case.

Fig. 18. GHG emissions from heating and cooling of HVAC systems in different locations.

manufacturing HVAC systems, thereby contributing to the mitigation of GHG emissions.

To further investigate the effect of HVAC characteristics on GHG emissions, the COP and EER which measure the heating and cooling efficiencies of the HVAC systems are varied in the range of $\pm 10\%$ – $\pm 30\%$ from the baseline values in Table 3. As shown in Fig. 17, GHG emissions decrease consistently with increasing COP and EER, resulting from lower electricity consumption at higher energy efficiencies of HVAC systems. With 30% increase in COP, total GHG emissions is reduced by 7.7% from 1.74×10^6 kg CO₂ equivalent to 1.61×10^6 kg CO₂ equivalent in the baseline case, and by 4.6% from 2.22×10^5 kg CO₂ equivalent to 2.12×10^5 kg CO₂ equivalent in the alternative case. When

increasing the EER by 30%, the GHG emissions can be reduced by 6.4% and 3.8% for the baseline and alternative cases, respectively. Overall, improving COP yields greater emission reduction potential than an equivalent rise in EER. In contrast, decreases in these parameters significantly increase GHG emissions, which highlights the importance of enhancing HVAC system energy efficiencies to achieve better environmental performance.

Beyond assessing a specific case in Sines, Portugal, this study also evaluates the environmental impacts of workplace HVAC systems in different cities, i.e., Paris, London, and Oslo, representing warm and cold climate zones. To be in accordance with EN 16798-1:2019 standard for energy performance of buildings [78], the heating and cooling set point temperatures in Paris are set as same as in Sines, at 18 °C and 25 °C, respectively, while for London and Oslo, the set point temperatures are set at 20 °C for heating and 25 °C for cooling. The total heating and cooling durations over one year, derived from historical daily average temperature data [64], are estimated as 202 and 53 days for Paris, 212 and 20 days for London, and 266 and 17 days for Oslo. Fig. 18 shows that GHG emissions associated with heating are highest in Oslo because of its long heating season. In warmer locations such as Sines and Paris, the longer cooling durations lead to more GHG emissions from cooling demand. These findings suggest that in regions with substantial heating demand, the adoption of high-efficiency and cleaner heating technologies, such as air/water source heat pump, waste heat recovery systems, and district heating network, can mitigate the emissions. Meanwhile, in these locations which also have lower cooling requirements, opportunities exist to reduce active cooling loads through recovering cooling energy from various cold energy sources, e.g., seawater.

Given the anticipated growth in renewable energy use for self-utilisation within the industrial district, two future scenarios involving

Fig. 19. Comparison of LCIA results for different electricity generation mixes.

increased renewable energy capacity and infrastructure development are considered. Future Scenario 1 investigated a near-term plan to expand solar PV capacity to 6.5 MW and develop 12.5 MW onshore wind capacity by 2030. Future Scenario 2 explored a long-term plan to build a 10 MW solar PV plant and 25 MW onshore wind capacity by 2050. In both scenarios, batteries will be deployed to support onsite energy storage and electricity consumption. Therefore, the environmental impacts of electricity supply under these two future scenarios are assessed and compared with the baseline and alternative cases to understand the implications of expanded renewable energy capacity.

Fig. 19 illustrates LCIA results for baseline and alternative cases, and two future scenarios with different electricity generation mixes. The highest impact value is weighted as 100% and the smaller impact values are expressed as percentages relative to the highest impact. The results exhibit that the baseline case yields the highest environmental burdens across all impact categories. Although only around 24% of electricity is generated from natural gas and oil in Portugal, this fraction has significantly contributed to overall environmental impacts. For electricity generation mixes involving 100% renewable energy, the pronounced impacts are shown in the impacts of mineral and metal resources use, land use, freshwater eutrophication, and non-cancer human toxicity. A decreasing trend is observed in the LCIA results with the increased capacity of renewable energy. Furthermore, Future Scenarios 1 and 2 show similar impact profiles, which implies the limited sensitivity of LCIA results to renewable installed capacity because the functional unit is based on the product system not on the full electricity generation capacity. These findings highlight the necessity of further evaluation on the cost expenditures associated with construction and operation of renewable electricity facilities, as these parameters would be influential for future transition towards renewable electricity generation.

5. Conclusions

This study develops a comprehensive LCA of the product system, i.e., solar-powered HVAC systems integrated with EV chargers in the workplace. By investigating full life environmental impacts of EV chargers, HVAC systems, solar PV plant, the environmental feasibility of renewable-powered EV chargers and HVAC systems was analysed and compared against national grid electricity. Influential key parameters regarding manufacturing, operation, and end-of-life disposal of the product system were compared to identify their impacts on LCIA results. Further discussion on the HVAC energy characteristics, the application of similar HVAC systems across different climate zones using European city case studies, and scenarios for future renewable electricity generation scenarios were presented to provide insights into mitigating environmental burdens.

The significant implications observed in this study are summarised: (a) the manufacturing and operation phases associated with the grid electricity are the primary contributors to most environmental impact categories; (b) in contrast, solar-powered product system has more dominate impacts on the manufacturing phase and substantially reduce environmental impacts, specifically reducing climate change impact by 87.28% in kg CO₂ equivalent compared to grid-supplied system; (c) sensitivity analyses reveal that the system lifespan and weight strongly affect ozone depletion for HVAC systems and the use of mineral and metal resources for EV chargers, the heating and cooling set point temperatures of HVAC systems have the most significant effect on the LCIA results, and solar irradiance predominantly influences land use; (d) reclaiming and reusing refrigerants from HVAC systems can reduce GWP 100 by 5.8% during the manufacturing phase of HVAC systems; (e) improving energy efficiency of HVAC systems and optimising the heating and cooling durations according to specific climate zones are crucial for reducing GHG emissions; (f) increased renewable electricity capacity can decrease LCIA results of the product system but have salient impacts in use of mineral and metal resources, land use, freshwater eutrophication, and non-cancer human toxicity.

The study is limited by the operational profiles of HVAC systems and EV chargers which represent non-optimised energy consumption patterns and system designs. Future studies could focus on the following aspects:

- Incorporating system optimisation strategies such as optimal control of HVAC operation and smart EV charging and discharging to observe potential improvements in LCIA outcomes.
- Considering dynamic heating and cooling conditions to better represent realistic building operation and its influence on environmental performance.
- Integrating cost factors such as the capital and operating cost of components within the integrated system to enable a more comprehensive environmental and economic assessment model.
- Exploring energy storage installations with renewable electricity to support more grid-independent EV-charging-integrated HVAC systems.

Overall, renewable energy-based HVAC systems integrated with EV chargers in office buildings can deliver environmental benefits extending beyond the mitigation in climate change and fossil resource depletion. Findings from LCIA results emphasise broader environmental impacts relevant to long-term environmental sustainability and can inform regulatory decisions on future development and application of sustainable energy systems in office buildings in different climate zones.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve the manuscript's language. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take (s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ruiqi Wang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Janie Ling-Chin:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Dibyendu Roy:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Anthony Paul Roskilly:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2026.127485>.

Data availability

Our supporting research dataset is published in the Durham University Research Data Repository. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.15128/r2v692t626d>.

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